

FATIGUE DELAMINATION OF A CARBON FABRIC–REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITE WITH CARBON NANOTUBES

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Keywords: Fatigue, Delamination, Composite, Carbon nanotubes

ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy composites are used in aerospace applications as primary aircraft structures where material fatigue can be an issue. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) appear to enhance the fatigue resistance according to literature. This work presents the results of precise crack growth rate measurement on double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens made from a carbon fibre fabric-reinforced epoxy composite. Two plates were evaluated where the resin was enhanced using 0.5 % CNTs and a flame retardant for one of the plates. Loading in mode I was displacement controlled with $R = 0.1$, $f = 4$ Hz and a constant maximum strain energy release rate $(G_I)_{\max}$ during the cycle. The value of $(G_I)_{\max}$ was defined to be 20 % up to 60 % of the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness. The crack length was determined from the modified compliance calibration (MCC) method by video-recording the specimen edges. The specimens enhanced by CNTs had a significantly decreased fatigue crack growth rate by approximately 80 %. The crack growth rate was also observed to be related to the interface of the weft and warp tows of the plain weave. Interlaminar fracture features and agglomerated CNTs were observed using a scanning electron microscope. Delamination extension during fatigue was analytically modelled using the relation of the delamination growth rate to the maximum value of the strain energy release rate. The understanding of crack growth rate in carbon fabric reinforced composites is crucial, especially when adopting the damage tolerance philosophy for use in an aircraft structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of carbon fibre-reinforced polymer composites in the aerospace industry is advantageous because of their high strength to weight ratio. The reduction of fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions can be achieved by this aspect [1]. To decrease the environmental impact of transport through efficient use of these materials, there is a need to solve certain technical issues in the aeronautical industry, such as low electrical conductivity, low toughness, and poor interlaminar properties. Effective solutions can be found in nanotechnology. Several authors have observed that nanofillers in the resin improved both the electrical and flame resistance properties [2, 3]. The increased electrical conductivity enables failure detection and monitoring in the polymer matrix composites where carbon nanotube (CNT) electrical networks are created [4].

The addition of CNTs to polymers reinforced with continuous micro-fibres only has an effect on those composite qualities that are controlled by the properties of their matrix. The stiffness, strength, and strain to failure in the fibre direction are only slightly affected. Some authors have introduced CNTs into the composite and have improved the shear strength [5], the impact resistance [6], the fracture toughness [7], and the fatigue characteristics [8]. These attributes support the reliability and the effective use of the composite in a new generation of aerospace structures. When the nanotubes are stirred correctly and are not agglomerated, a polymer matrix has better adhesion to the fibres, which could be the primary reason for the improvement of the previously listed attributes. The CNTs create a new component in the fibre: a matrix system that makes the synergic effect more apparent. However, the nanotube walls have an extremely small surface energy, which creates problems with the creation of bonds with the polymer. The creation of nanotube agglomerations, which is associated with Van der

Walls forces and the high length to diameter ratio of the nanotubes, is a problem that makes the demanding effect difficult to attain [9]. A possible solution is the functionalization of nanotubes, which means a chemical change in the CNT surface.

This study attempts to investigate fatigue crack growth behaviour of CFRP plates that are typically used in aerospace structures considering CNT and flame retardant additives. The crack growth was observed on double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens loaded in mode I using sinusoidal cycles. The modified compliance calibration (MCC) method was used for detailed crack length evaluation. Fracture surface analysis was used to support the investigation. The response of the crack growth rate on the fracture interface was also investigated.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Material properties

Two CFRP plates were provided for the experiments. The resin was enhanced using 0.5 % of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) and a flame retardant for one of the plates. The epoxy matrix used to manufacture the panels was prepared by mixing an epoxy precursor, tetraglycidylmethylenedianiline (TGMDA), with an epoxy reactive flexibilizer 1-4 butanedioldiglycidyl ether (BDE) at a ratio of 80:20 (by wt.). The presence of BDE in the epoxy mixture has proven to be very effective in improving the nanofiller dispersion due to a decrease in the viscosity [10, 11] and, in addition, BDE has been found to reduce the moisture content, which is a critical characteristic for aeronautic materials [12].

The flame resistance of the epoxy mixture was improved by using 5 wt.% of glycidyl POSS (GPOSS), which is viscous liquid that is functionalized with oxirane rings and belonging to the class of polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane compounds [13]. Epoxy blend and DDS were mixed at 120°C and MWCNTs were added and incorporated into the matrix using ultrasonication for 20 min. The epoxy mixture used to manufacture the panels was filled with 0.5 wt.% of MWCNTs for which the mixture is beyond the electrical percolation threshold [14]. This formulation was used to manufacture CFRCs using resin film infusion (RFI) with an unusual technique to infuse a nano-filled resin into a dry carbon fibre preform. This new technique allows us to overcome drawbacks related to non-optimal values of the viscosity for the RFI process.

The laminate was made with 24 plies of a plain weave carbon fibre fabric (SIGMATEX (UK) LDT 193GSM /PW /HTA40 E13 3K) with a sequence of lamination (0/90°) such that the fabric was quasi-isotropic and balanced. Table 1 shows selected measured properties of the material used.

Plate	Laminate thickness h (mm)	Resin density (g/cm ³)	Resin additives	v_f (%)	v_m (%)	$void$ (%)	E-modulus in tension (GPa)	E-modulus in bending (GPa)
blank	(4.01 ±0.07)	1.285	-	67.4	31.6	1.0	69.14	90.81
CNT	(4.17 ±0.04)	1.276	0.5 % CNTs, 5 % GPOSS	64.6	35.2	0.2	67.13	87.99

Table 1: Measured laminate properties including the volume fractions of the plates used for the specimen extraction.

2.2 Specimens and test procedure

Testing was performed on DCB specimens with a width B of 20 mm and a length of 185 mm. Booth edges of the specimen were painted using a thin white colour and were marked using lines with an interval of 5 mm. The specimens were clamped using bonded aluminium blocks into a INOVA ZUZ 100 loading machine with a LTC-116-0.1 load cell, which has a capacity of 1 kN and is appropriate for dynamic loading (Fig. 1). The end of the specimen was supported by a flexible wire to

maintain the specimen in the horizontal direction and to reduce any additional forces that could originate from the specimen weight.

Figure 1: a) Test set up of the double cantilever beam (DCB) loading with the attached video cameras used for the fatigue crack length measurement, b) parameters of a DCB specimen with loading blocks.

A pair of video cameras each having a resolution of 2048 x 1536 pixels and measuring at 12.5 frames per second focused on the edges to cover approximately 15 mm of the specimen length. The theoretical resolution was approximately 7 $\mu\text{m}/\text{px}$. However, the precision of the crack measurement from the front was affected by partial fibre bridging in certain areas. The time of the cameras and the loading machine was synchronized manually before measurement.

The test was performed at room temperature. The fatigue test procedure was based on a draft standard that is being prepared for ASTM International. This procedure is well described in the article [15]. The initial load was applied with a constant crosshead displacement of 5 mm/min until a delamination occurred within the first 5 mm of the propagated length. Next, the specimen was unloaded. Using a simple data fit of the linear part of load-displacement curve, the displacement was zeroed at a new value that corresponded with the fitted zero force. This step was performed because the displacement controlled cycling could cause negative force values for very low displacements when the displacement was not zeroed properly. The crack propagation during the following loading was monitored using video cameras (Fig. 1). Sinusoidal loading with displacement control set to δ_{max} and δ_{min} according to Table 2, and a frequency of 4 Hz was applied. Load P and displacement δ were recorded by the INOVA machine at frequency of 100 Hz. The recorded files typically had 10^7 rows of data and were processed using a MATLAB script that evaluated maximum force in each cycle and then averaged the maximum force over approximately 100 cycles to reduce the number of data points.

Specimen	$(G_I)_{\text{max}}$	δ_{max}	δ_{min}	δ_{max} (mm)	δ_{min} (mm)
1	blank 1	40 % of G_{Ic}	$(0.4 \delta_{cr}^2)^{1/2}$	5.06	0.51
2	blank 2	50 % of G_{Ic}	$(0.5 \delta_{cr}^2)^{1/2}$	5.66	0.57
3	blank 3	50 % of G_{Ic}	$(0.5 \delta_{cr}^2)^{1/2}$	5.66	0.57
4	blank 4	60 % of G_{Ic}	$(0.6 \delta_{cr}^2)^{1/2}$	6.20	0.62
5	CNT 1	20 % of G_{Ic}	$(0.2 \delta_{cr}^2)^{1/2}$	3.56	0.36
6	CNT 2	30 % of G_{Ic}	$(0.3 \delta_{cr}^2)^{1/2}$	4.36	0.44
7	CNT 3	50 % of G_{Ic}	$(0.5 \delta_{cr}^2)^{1/2}$	5.63	0.56
8	CNT 4	60 % of G_{Ic}	$(0.6 \delta_{cr}^2)^{1/2}$	6.17	0.62

Table 2: Parameters of sinusoidal loading with $R = 0.1$ controlled by the displacement δ . The mean $\delta_{cr} = 8.00$ mm for a blank and 7.96 mm for the CNT (obtained from static testing on 5 specimens per series using ASTM D5228).

The crack propagation length for the individual specimens used for the compliance calibration was determined from the snapshots of the video recording. The length was measured from the picture using a custom-made program with a virtual gauge. ASTM D5528 standard [16] was used to evaluate the results. The modified compliance calibration (MCC) described in the standard was used for data reduction. This method was selected because it considers a specimen thickness that was slightly different for the two series. The constants, A_1 and k from Eq. (1), were determined for individual specimens using a least square fit applied to the plot of the optically observed delamination lengths a versus the cube root of the corresponding compliance C . For each specimen, the constants were used specifically for one specimen. The relationship between the compliance and the delamination length for the MCC solution is

$$a/h = A_1 \cdot C^{1/3} + k, \quad (1)$$

where the compliance C is δ_{\max}/P_{\max} and h is the specimen thickness. The fitted constants A_1 and k were used for the crack length determination for each cycle using Eq. (1) based on the continuous P_{\max} recorded from the test machine. δ_{\max} was constant during loading. The compliance calibration is shown in a detail in Fig. 2. This figure also shows the continuous crack length calculated from the fitted constants.

Figure 2: Crack length determination based on the modified compliance calibration from the optically measured values on specimen blank 1.

Each fatigue specimen was cycled until the delamination growth rate had decreased to at least 10^{-7} m/cycle. A polynomial method was used to calculate the crack growth rate $\Delta a/\Delta N$. The method calculated $\Delta a/\Delta N$ by fitting a second-order polynomial to each set of 29 successive data points. The polynomial was used to calculate the value at the midpoint of the 29-point data set. The corresponding $(G_I)_{\max}$ value was calculated from equation (2), where P_{\max} is the value at the midpoint of the data set, and B is the specimen width. The equation is the following:

$$(G_I)_{\max} = \frac{3P_{\max}^2 C^{2/3}}{2BhA_1} \quad (2)$$

2.3 Modelling of delamination growth

Several relations are proposed to characterize the delamination growth during cycling [19]. The number of cycles during stable delamination growth is generally obtained from the relationship that is similar to Paris' law used in the description of crack kinetic of metals. Although ΔG is widely used in methodologies [20], $(G_I)_{\max}$ is used in the ASTM draft standard [15] and similarly in this paper. The delamination increment da per cycle increment dN is expressed as a power function of the maximum strain energy release rate $(G_I)_{\max}$ at the delamination front at the peak loading in a cycle as follows:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C \cdot (G_I)_{\max}^n \quad (3)$$

Constants C and n are determined by fitting the function values of the relationship (3) to the experimental data. In practical application, the incremental form of equation (3) is used. The delamination length a in applied cycle k is obtained from cycle-by-cycle integration according to equation (4), where a_0 is the initial delamination length.

$$a_k = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k C \cdot (G_I)_{\max i}^n \quad (4)$$

3 RESULTS

3.1 Crack growth rate analysis

Plots of the crack growth rate $\Delta a/\Delta N$ vs. $(G_I)_{\max}$ were generated for all the fatigue specimens from both series. Figure 4 shows the results for four specimens from each series tested at a specific load level between 20 and 60 % of G_{Ic} . Because of the scatter and variable growth rate of the data sets, these values are not very useful for generating a valid Paris law. However, boundary lines were drawn in the plot for the two series that shows that there was greater data scatter for the blank specimens. By comparing the middle sections of the boundaries, we can state that there was a decrease in the crack growth rate of approximately 95 % for $(G_I)_{\max} = 200 \text{ J/m}^2$. The effect was lower for the increased load level of 300 J/m^2 where the rate decreased by approximately 70 %.

Figure 4: Delamination growth results in the $\Delta a/\Delta N$ vs. $(G_I)_{\max}$ plot. The CNT+GPOSS series had a significantly lower crack growth rate.

There were significant accelerations and retardations of the delamination apparent from the measurements that caused very high variations of the rate between 10^{-10} and 10^{-8} m/cycle, as seen in Fig. 4. Fig. 5 shows the relation of the crack growth rate to the crack length. The changes in global rate were correlated with the fracture surface. The delamination crack at the woven-fabric laminate interface normally had multiple crack fronts. The crack front was apparently accelerated on the $0^\circ/0^\circ$ interface. This effect was always prevalent for the global rate. The most significant retardation was present when the crack reached the end of the $0^\circ/0^\circ$ interface where it reached boundaries along the complete crack front. The global curve also showed minor retardations on the transitions to the $90^\circ/0^\circ$ and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces. This behaviour was previously described theoretically in [17]. The delamination preferentially extends parallel to the fibres and is impeded at the weft.

Figure 5: Effect of multiple crack fronts at the woven-fabric laminate interface identified in correlation with the global fatigue crack growth rate curve (specimen blank 1).

3.2 Fractography

Two specimens were observed using the scanning electron microscope (SEM) in secondary electron imaging to recognize the origin of the black spots visible on the fracture surface of the CNT-enhanced specimens. Figure 6 shows the macro-morphology of the specimen blank 1 and CNT 1. Figure 7 shows the results of the microfractographic analysis. Figure 7a presents the overall fracture surface within the fatigue section with bright spots that are visually black. Figure 7b shows a detail of the spot with some resin features, such as resin scarps between the fibre imprints and gouges caused by an adjacent layer of perpendicular fibres beneath the visualised surface. Figure 7c presents a detail of the spot boundary where a significant difference between the fractures is visible. Ragged resin clouds and rough fibre imprints within the spot are in contrast to the smooth resin out of the spot. Finally, Figure 7d shows agglomerated CNTs within the spot and blank resin out of the spot area. The porosity is also evident.

Figure 6: Macro-morphology of the a) blank 1 and the b) CNT 1 specimens. The black spots on the CNT specimen are CNT agglomerates, which were shown on the SEM.

Figure 7: a) Fracture surface with bright spots that are visually black, b) a detail of the spot with some resin features, c) a detail of the spot boundary, d) agglomerated CNTs within the spot and the blank resin out of the spot area.

3.3 Model of delamination curves

The simulation of the delamination growth is presented on two blank specimens. The experimental results of the delamination growth in the form of $\Delta a/\Delta N$ vs. $(G_I)_{\max}$ shown in Fig. 4 were used as input data for growth rate estimation. These data of delamination growth rate were fitted using a least square estimation to smooth the resulting curve expressed by equation (3) and used for the whole range of $(G_I)_{\max}$. No critical and threshold values were assumed because the analysis performed is in the range of the measured data in which no tendency to a limiting value was observed. The simulation results of the delamination growth are presented for two blank test specimens in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Modelled and experimental results for two blank specimens: a) specimen loaded at a constant cross head displacement $\delta_{\max} = 5.66$ mm, b) specimen loaded at a constant cross head displacement $\delta_{\max} = 5.06$ mm.

The crack growth rate dependence on $(G_I)_{\max}$, which was determined according to equations (1-2), was greater, which resulted in greater simulated delamination growth. Therefore, a correction of the delamination length $|\Delta|$ was applied using the modified beam theory (MBT) method [16] of G_I determination. Assuming a constant delamination length correction of $|\Delta| = -8$ mm resulted in a sufficient data match of the delamination growth curves shown in Fig. 8.

4 DISCUSSION

The observed improved fatigue behaviour measured for the CNT + GPOSS additions could be caused by either of these two compounds. However, CNTs were observed on the fracture surface, so it appears that the CNTs caused the improvement. Previously, the authors in [18] showed that the crack propagation rate decreased by 69 % for 0.3 % of CNTs, and these results agree very well with the presented results in which a decrease of 70 % up to 95 % for 0.5 % CNTs was observed.

The different decrease in the crack growth rate for low and high loading levels can be explained by the fact that, at low load levels, the crack propagates slower and, thus, is more affected by the microstructure enhanced by the compounds. This resulted in a more significant effect due to the CNTs. For high load levels, the crack propagates in larger steps, weakens the effect of the microstructure and diminishes the effect of the compounds.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The CNT+GPOSS addition in the resin caused a decrease in the fatigue crack growth rate by approximately 80 %. Agglomerated CNTs were observed on the fracture surface and were visually observable as large black spots. The delamination crack growth rate relationship with respect to the woven ply fracture interface was experimentally measured.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The research leading to these results was funded by the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under Grant Agreement N° 313978. The authors would like to thank Liberata Guadagno and Umberto Vietri from University of Salerno for their support with this project. CIRA GROUP is also gratefully acknowledged for the composite panels manufacturing.

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